

Standardization of some ophthalmic drugs with pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) reagent

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Manuscript received 29 March 2011, revised 14 October 2011, accepted 08 November 2011

Abstract : In the present paper we have reported a simple and convenient titrimetric method for determination of ophthalmic drugs e.g. cyclopentolate hydrochloride, atropine sulphate, gentamycin sulphate, norfloxacin, ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and tobramycin sulphate in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations such as cyclate (Dps), cyclogik (Dps), ATP (Dps), tropine (Dps), genta swift (Dps), intragen (Dps), normax (Dps), norflox (Dps), adiflox (Dps), zoxan (Dps), toba (Dps) and tobramycin (Dps) with pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) reagent. Pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) is a versatile oxidizing agent of chromium(VI). The reagents being widely used as an oxidant for several classes of organic and medicinal compounds. The value of percentage error, coefficient of variation (CV) and standard deviation (SD) prove the method to be precise and reproducible. To establish authenticity of the method, recovery experiments were also carried out by standard drug addition method.

Keywords : Ophthalmic drugs, pharmaceutical preparations, pyridinium fluorochromate, oxidizing agent, titration.

Introduction

A variety of compounds containing chromium(VI) have proved to be versatile oxidizing reagents¹. Extensive work has to the development of a good number of these oxidants such as the Collins reagent², chromium trioxide-3,5-dimethylpyrazole complex³, pyridinium chlorochromate⁴, pyridinium dichromate⁵, 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate⁶, pyridinium fluorochromate^{7,8}, quinolinium fluorochromate⁹, quinolinium chlorochromate¹⁰, 3,5-dimethylpyrazolium fluorochromate¹¹, 2,6-dicarboxypyridinium chlorochromate^{12,13}, N-methylpiperidinium chlorochromate¹⁴, tetramethylammonium fluorochromate¹⁵ and benzyltrimethylammonium fluorochromate¹⁶.

Industrial demand has many workers to reach for more ideal oxidants with a number of specifications including : lower cost, higher yields, better selectivity, milder neutral conditions, easier preparations, high solubility, less toxicity and quick reaction. Among the above mentioned reagents²⁻¹⁶, PFC has an edge over others for rendering higher yields under near neutral conditions. In the present work we chose pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) as an oxidizing reagent which was synthesized by us following literature procedure¹⁷.

Different types of ophthalmics have different actions in different diseases. An antimusearinic agent such as cyclopentolate hydrochloride, atropine sulphate and tropicamide are used as eye drops to produce cycloplegia and mydriasis. Ophthalmic drugs of aminoglycoside group such as gentamycin sulphate, tobramycin sulphate and neomycin sulphate are active against Gram-negative bacteria. Fluoroquinolone antibacterial agents such as ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin are active against Gram-positive bacteria.

Materials and methods :

Reagents and solutions :

Pyridinium fluorochromate solution (0.03 N) : Pyridinium fluorochromate (495 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (Merck) (150 mL) and made up to the volume with distilled water in 250 mL volumetric flask. The solution was standardized iodometrically. Sodium thiosulphate solution (0.01 N) was prepared and standardized by 0.01 N potassium dichromate solution iodometrically. Potassium iodide : (10% w/v aqueous solution) and starch solution : (1% w/v aqueous solution) were also prepared.

Sample solution : Accurately weighed 100 mg pure

samples as well as pharmaceutical samples of cyclopentolate hydrochloride and atropine sulphate were dissolved in minimum amount of ether and gentamycin sulphate, norfloxacin, ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and tobramycin sulphate in minimum amount of distilled water. After getting a clear solution the flask was made up to the mark with distilled water. While diluting with distilled water every care was taken to keep the solution homogeneous.

Drop solutions : The solution contents of the drops equivalent to 100 mg of the pure sample were taken into 100 mL volumetric flask and dissolved in minimum amount of solvent and made up with distilled water to get a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

Procedure :

Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the samples were taken in 100 mL stoppered conical flask, pyridinium fluorochromate reagent (0.03 N) (5 mL) and 5 N H₂SO₄ (10 mL) was added to it. The reaction mixture was shaken thoroughly and allowed to react for required reaction time e.g. gentamycin sulphate for 5 min, cyclopentolate hydrochloride, atropine sulphate, ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, norfloxacin for 10 min and tobramycin sulphate for 15 min at room temperature (25–30 °C). After the reaction was over, 10% KI solution (5 mL) was added to it, contents shaken thoroughly and allowed to stand for 1 min. The liberated iodine was titrated with 0.01 N sodium thiosulphate using starch as indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample recovered was calculated by the difference in the titre values of sodium thiosulphate solution for blank and actual experiment.

Calculation :

For each experiment, the amount of the compound was calculated by following expression :

$$\text{mg of sample} = \frac{M \times N(B - S)}{n}$$

where, *M* = molecular wt. of the sample, *N* = normality of sodium thiosulphate solution, *B* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for blank, *S* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample, *n* = stoichiometry of the reaction.

For testing quantitative validity of the recommended

method, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) were also calculated for each sample size. At least nine determinations were carried out and the results noted. The method was authenticated by carrying out recovery experiments through standard drug addition method. A known amount of the pure compound was taken and varying amounts of the pharmaceutical preparations of the same compounds were added to it and total amount of the sample was found out by the following expression.

$$\% \text{ recovery} = \frac{N(\Sigma XY) - (\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)}{N(\Sigma X^2) - (\Sigma X)^2} \times 100$$

where, *N* = ΣN = total number of observations, *X* = amount of drug added, *Y* = amount of drug obtained by calculation, $\Sigma X = \Sigma NX$, $\Sigma Y = \Sigma NY$, $\Sigma XY = \Sigma(NX)(Y)$, $\Sigma X^2 = \Sigma(NX)(X)$.

The determinations were done with different sample amounts (i.e. 1–10 mg) but for convenience, results were shown only with 1, 3 and 5 mg (Table 1).

Results and discussion

It was found that different stoichiometric ratios were obtained in different ophthalmics such as cyclopentolate hydrochloride (1 : 4), atropine sulphate (1 : 4), gentamycin sulphate (1 : 2), norfloxacin (1 : 2), ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (1 : 4) and tobramycin sulphate (1 : 6) in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations. The value remains constant even under varying reaction conditions i.e. change in reaction time, concentration of the reagent, reaction medium, reaction temperature etc. It was observed that all the ophthalmic drugs required 10 min to complete the reaction except gentamycin sulphate and tobramycin sulphate which needed 5 and 15 min respectively. This may be due to difference in their structures. There was no effect of reaction time on the recovery of the sample. A lesser reaction time (below 5–15 min) gave higher percentage of error because of incomplete reaction, while increased reaction time (above 15 min) did not improve the results. The effect of concentration of pyridinium fluorochromate reagent (0.1–1.0 N) was also studied and it was found that the recommended concentration (0.03 N) was suitable for accurate and consistent results. While studying the effect of sulphuric acid upon

Table 1. Milligram determination of some ophthalmics (pure sample) and their pharmaceutical preparations with ($3 \times 10^{-2} N$) PFC reagent in acidic medium

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (mL)	Amount present ^a (mg)	Reaction time (min)	Molarity	Amount obtained by calculation ^b (mg)	Error (%)	SD (\pm)	CV
1.	Cyclopentolate (Pure)	1.00	0.982	10	4	0.972	1.02	0.0039	0.4012
		3.00	2.946	10	4	2.928	0.61	0.0048	0.1639
		5.00	4.910	10	4	4.890	0.41	0.0030	0.0613
A.	Cyclate (Dps) Zy. Cadila	1.00	0.908	10	4	0.898	1.10	0.0042	0.4677
		3.00	2.724	10	4	2.707	0.62	0.0022	0.0813
		5.00	4.540	10	4	4.523	0.37	0.0031	0.0685
B.	Cyclogik (Dps) FDC	1.00	0.931	10	4	0.921	1.07	0.0015	0.1629
		3.00	2.793	10	4	2.775	0.64	0.0013	0.0468
		5.00	4.655	10	4	4.637	0.39	0.0015	0.0323
2.	Atropine sulphate (Pure)	1.00	0.979	10	4	0.969	1.02	0.0036	0.3715
		3.00	2.937	10	4	2.916	0.72	0.0031	0.1063
		5.00	4.895	10	4	4.873	0.45	0.0019	0.0340
A.	ATP (Dps) BioMicron	1.00	0.921	10	4	0.911	1.09	0.0016	0.1756
		3.00	2.763	10	4	2.741	0.80	0.0024	0.0876
		5.00	4.605	10	4	4.588	0.37	0.0027	0.0588
B.	Atropine (Dps) Neon Labs	1.00	0.929	10	4	0.919	1.08	0.0026	0.2829
		3.00	2.787	10	4	2.770	0.61	0.0023	0.0830
		5.00	4.645	10	4	4.626	0.41	0.0020	0.0432
3.	Gentamycin sulphate (Pure)	1.00	0.953	5	2	0.943	1.05	0.0038	0.3712
		3.00	2.859	5	2	2.841	0.63	0.0028	0.0986
		5.00	4.765	5	2	4.747	0.38	0.0019	0.0400
A.	Genta Swift (Dps) Ind Swift	1.00	0.916	5	2	0.906	1.09	0.0028	0.3091
		3.00	2.748	5	2	2.727	0.76	0.0036	0.1320
		5.00	4.580	5	2	4.555	0.55	0.0022	0.0483
B.	Intragen (Dps) Intra Labs	1.00	0.922	5	2	0.912	1.08	0.0041	0.4496
		3.00	2.766	5	2	2.748	0.65	0.0028	0.1019
		5.00	4.610	5	2	4.592	0.39	0.0034	0.0740
4.	Norfloxacin (Pure)	1.00	0.966	10	2	0.956	1.04	0.0026	0.2720
		3.00	2.898	10	2	2.879	0.66	0.0019	0.0660
		5.00	4.830	10	2	4.809	0.43	0.0035	0.0728
A.	Normax (Dps) IPCA	1.00	0.925	10	2	0.915	1.08	0.0025	0.2732
		3.00	2.775	10	2	2.755	0.72	0.0032	0.1162
		5.00	4.625	10	2	4.607	0.39	0.0030	0.0651
B.	Norflox (Dps) Cipla	1.00	0.939	10	2	0.929	1.06	0.0019	0.2045
		3.00	2.817	10	2	2.800	0.60	0.0030	0.1071
		5.00	4.695	10	2	4.677	0.38	0.0026	0.0566
5.	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (Pure)	1.00	0.988	10	4	0.978	1.01	0.0047	0.4806
		3.00	2.964	10	4	2.944	0.67	0.0035	0.1189
		5.00	4.940	10	4	4.919	0.43	0.0039	0.0793
A.	Adiflox (Dps) Intas	1.00	0.899	10	4	0.890	1.00	0.0031	0.3483
		3.00	2.697	10	4	2.678	0.70	0.0022	0.0822
		5.00	4.495	10	4	4.479	0.36	0.0020	0.0447

Table-1 (contd.)

B.	Zoxan (Dps)	1.00	0.902	10	4	0.892	1.11	0.0018	0.2018
	FDC	3.00	2.706	10	4	2.689	0.63	0.0023	0.0855
		5.00	4.510	10	4	4.493	0.38	0.0019	0.0423
6.	Tobramycin	1.00	0.997	15	6	0.987	1.00	0.0029	0.2938
	sulphate	3.00	2.991	15	6	2.972	0.64	0.0021	0.0707
	(Pure)	5.00	4.985	15	6	4.964	0.42	0.0031	0.0624
A.	Toba (Dps)	1.00	0.952	15	6	0.942	1.05	0.0019	0.2017
	Sun Parma	3.00	2.856	15	6	2.835	0.74	0.0018	0.0635
		5.00	4.760	15	6	4.740	0.42	0.0029	0.0612
B	Tobramycin (Dps)	1.00	0.933	15	6	0.923	1.04	0.0016	0.1733
	Intas	3.00	2.799	15	6	2.782	0.61	0.0020	0.0719
		5.00	4.665	15	6	4.643	0.47	0.0026	0.0560

Dps = Drops, SD = Standard Deviation, CV = Coefficient of Variation.

^aIn each sample nine estimations were done. ^bAverage of nine determinations.

For every sample of ophthalmic drugs e.g. cyclopentolate hydrochloride, atropine sulphate, gentamycin sulphate, norfloxacin, ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and tobramycin sulphate, recovery experiment were also done by standard drug addition method and the results were reported (Tables 2-6).

Table 2. Recovery studies of cyclopentolate hydrochloride by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
1.	3	0.982	0.954	1.966	0.962	0.918	0.910	99.15
2.	3	0.982	1.962	2.975	1.873	3.675	3.849	
3.	3	0.982	2.883	3.949	2.841	8.191	8.312	
4.	3	0.982	3.801	4.956	3.786	14.391	14.450	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.600$		$\Sigma Y = 9.462$	$\Sigma XY = 27.175$	$\Sigma X^2 = 27.521$	

Table 3. Recovery studies of atropine sulphate by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
1.	3	0.979	0.957	1.959	0.970	0.928	0.916	99.68
2.	3	0.979	1.979	2.966	1.988	3.934	3.916	
3.	3	0.979	2.986	3.970	2.959	8.836	8.916	
4.	3	0.979	3.969	4.981	3.962	15.725	15.753	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.891$		$\Sigma Y = 9.879$	$\Sigma XY = 29.423$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.501$	

Table 4. Recovery studies of gentamycin sulphate by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
1.	3	0.953	0.982	1.972	0.980	0.962	0.964	99.43
2.	3	0.953	1.988	2.954	1.963	3.902	3.952	
3.	3	0.953	2.975	3.966	2.964	8.818	8.851	
4.	3	0.953	3.970	4.970	3.948	15.674	15.761	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.915$		$\Sigma Y = 9.855$	$\Sigma XY = 29.356$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.528$	

Table 5. Recovery studies of norfloxacin by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
1.	3	0.988	0.981	1.976	0.992	0.973	0.962	99.37
2.	3	0.988	1.987	2.969	1.949	3.873	3.948	
3.	3	0.988	2.982	3.978	2.965	8.842	8.892	
4.	3	0.988	3.970	4.982	3.952	15.689	15.761	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.920$		$\Sigma Y = 9.858$	$\Sigma XY = 29.377$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.563$	

Table 6. Recovery studies of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
1.	3	0.988	0.981	1.972	0.996	0.977	0.962	99.23
2.	3	0.988	1.972	2.983	1.971	3.887	3.889	
3.	3	0.988	2.960	3.986	2.870	8.495	8.762	
4.	3	0.988	3.961	4.958	3.970	15.725	15.690	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.874$		$\Sigma Y = 9.807$	$\Sigma XY = 29.084$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.303$	

Table 7. Recovery studies of tobramycin sulphate by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
1.	3	0.997	0.977	1.956	0.984	0.961	0.955	99.75
2.	3	0.997	1.984	2.969	1.968	3.905	3.936	
3.	3	0.997	2.969	3.978	2.976	8.836	8.815	
4.	3	0.997	3.985	4.984	3.969	15.816	15.880	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.915$		$\Sigma Y = 9.897$	$\Sigma XY = 29.518$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.586$	

reaction it was found that in the absence of acid the reaction was very slow. When the concentration was increased from 1 N to 5 N the results improved but the sample recovery became constant at 5 N or beyond that. The next variation to be studied was reaction temperature from 0–80 °C. At ice cold temperature the reaction was very slow but fastens with rise in temperature but gave constant results at room temperature (25–30 °C). On heating the reaction mixture at higher temperature the result were erratic, perhaps due to loss of the reagent.

On the basis of available literature and stoichiometry established, a possible course of reaction may also be

suggested. Since the isolation and identification of final reaction product was not possible, it was assumed that the ophthalmic drugs were oxidized to their corresponding products.

Acknowledgement

The authors are greatly thankful to Ophtho Remedies Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd., Allahabad, India for providing ophthalmic compounds as gift samples. The author, Brijesh K. Singh and Vinod Kumar are also thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India for providing financial assistance in the form of research fellowships.

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